

FATIGUE BEHAVIOUR OF SHORT-FIBRE AND PARTICLE-REINFORCED METAL MATRIX COMPOSITES

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ABSTRACT

Studies of tensile and fatigue behaviour have been made on δ -alumina short-fibre-reinforced Al-3.5%Cu alloy and on α -silicon carbide-reinforced 6061 (Al-Mg-Si) and 2014 (Al-Cu-Mg) alloys. The fatigue life at a given stress, with all these composites, showed an improvement over the matrix alloy. This follows a pattern of the fatigue properties improving as the tensile strength of the composite increases. Differences in fatigue crack initiation and growth were found between the short-fibre and particulate-reinforced composites. The δ -alumina short fibres did not react with the matrix, and this allowed crack initiation at fibre ends and, when propagating the crack path deviated significantly as it encountered further fibres. At 10% (by volume) the silicon carbide particles themselves did not promote initiation nor cause a deviatory crack growth path. Enhanced elastic modulus and work-hardening rate were believed to have contributed to the improved fatigue behaviour of both composite types.

INTRODUCTION

The introduction of short fibres, whiskers or particles of ceramic materials, such as silicon carbide or alumina, into a metallic matrix can promote a significant change in mechanical properties. Some of these changes may be beneficial, e.g. improvements in elastic modulus, whilst others are deleterious, e.g. reduced toughness, particularly at high volume fractions of reinforcement. Fatigue properties in many materials do relate to elastic modulus, work hardening and to crack initiation and growth under monotonic loading conditions. Improvements in modulus are achieved in almost equal measure by the introduction of short fibres, whiskers or particles into an aluminium alloy matrix¹⁻³. Yielding in MMC's can be influenced by a large number of variables, such as size, shape and volume fraction of the reinforcement, type of alloy matrix and its heat-treated state, the coefficients of expansion of reinforcement and matrix, interfacial conditions and the processing route for the composite⁴. Matrix grain sizes, high dislocation densities and precipitation hardening assist in raising the yield stress, whilst residual matrix tensile stresses work against these positive factors. High rates of work hardening which follow, may obscure the low matrix yield.

Low fracture strains on MMC's are encouraged by high volume fractions of reinforcement of large aspect ratio, strong reinforcement-matrix interfacial bond strengths, strong matrix alloys and reinforcement with a small failure strain. Examination of fracture surfaces of MMC's containing either fibres or particles may reveal evidence of ductile failure of matrix, failure at fibre-matrix interface and brittle fractures of the reinforcement in different measures, depending on the conditions which exist at the interface²⁻⁴.

Improvements in fatigue properties have been shown to take place in some particle, whisker and discontinuous-fibre-reinforced composites^{3,5,6,7}. In some cases, stress amplitude versus number of stress cycle plots (S-N plots) obtained on samples tested under zero-tension cycling conditions have revealed a pattern of behaviour similar to

that found in monotonic tensile testing. If the reinforcements enhance the tensile strength beyond the value obtained upon the matrix alloy, then fatigue strength will also be increased. This has been found in a number of alloys where short fibre-matrix bonding has also been a variable⁵. In this paper, fatigue behaviour has been investigated on two composite types, i.e. a "Saffil" ϵ -alumina short-fibre-reinforced aluminium-copper alloy and on two α -silicon carbide-particle-reinforced aluminium alloys, Al-Cu-Mg (2014) and Al-Si-Mg (6061). The ϵ -Al₂O₃ reinforced Al-Cu alloy in the as-heat treated condition has fibres with an aspect ratio of 10:1, weak fibre-matrix bond strength and a matrix of intermediate strength. The composites containing equiaxed α -SiC particles have different tensile strengths, i.e. 6061 being the weaker than 2014 matrix, and interfaces of intermediate strength. Besides gaining fatigue data in the form of S-N plots, replication of fatigue sample surfaces and fractography will be carried out in order to determine crack initiation sites and propagation paths.

EXPERIMENTAL

1. Preparation of Materials

Two different techniques of fabrication for the two composite types were employed. The short-fibre ϵ -Al₂O₃-reinforced alloys were prepared by squeeze casting, and the particulate composites were produced by spray forming. "Saffil" (RF grade) ϵ -Al₂O₃ fibres (3 μ m diameter) were made up into preforms (0.6 g/cm³ density) and then inserted into a preheated die (220°C) prior to injection of superheated metal (\approx 750°C) at a pressure of 80 MPa in the squeeze-casting operation. In the spray-forming process, atomised droplets of the molten alloy were co-sprayed with α -SiC particles (\approx 10 μ m in size) on to a specially designed substrate. The sprayed ingot was hot and cold worked to provide 1 mm thick sheet. Nominal matrix alloy compositions and densities determined on matrices and composites are given in Table I. Heat treatment procedures are also detailed in Table I. This involved a sequence of solution treatment, cold water quenching and aging for periods up to 24 h. With the α -SiC-reinforced sheet, a cold straightening operation was sometimes carried out before the final aging treatment.

Table I Nominal composition, density and heat-treatment conditions

Alloy Type	Cu	Si	Mg	Mn	Al	Solution Treatment	Ageing Treatment	Density	
						°C, h	°C, h	M	C
2014	4.45	0.85	0.50	0.80	Remainder	505, 0.3	175, 12	2760, 2840	
6061	0.25	0.60	1.00	-	Remainder	525, 0.3	185, 8	2700, 2750	
Al-3.5%Cu	3.50	-	-	-	Remainder	520, 6	170, 24	2720, 2840	

(M - matrix, C - composite)

2. Tensile and Fatigue Testing

Round bar test pieces (diameter 6 mm, gauge length 35 mm) were machined from the squeeze cast materials. Flat tensile, test samples were cut and shaped from the spray formed 1 mm thick sheet materials (gauge length 40 mm, width 12 mm). A pair of strain gauges was mounted on to the gauge length of each sample and the load-extension plots were recorded.

Fatigue in zero-tension tests to determine S-N plots were carried out on samples of similar dimensions to those used for tensile tests, with the exception of the squeeze cast ϵ -Al₂O₃ composites where the specimen was waisted down to a diameter of 4 mm. The surfaces of the fatigue samples were ground to a 1200 grit finish. A Mayes servo-hydraulic machine was used to test the specimens under load control at a frequency of 10 Hz and at an R-ratio of 0.1.

Four-point bend tests were used to observe initiation and propagation of surface cracks. These employed 10 x 10 cross-section x 70 mm long bars which had been ground and polished (to a 1 μ m diamond finish). A frequency of 30 Hz and an R-ratio of 0.1 were employed in the tests. A surface replication technique, involving acetate sheets presoaked in acetone, was used at selected cycle intervals to find evidence of cracks. After peeling away the acetate sheet, it was subjected to gold-palladium coating to enhance the surface detail for examination by optical and scanning electron microscopy.

RESULTS

1. Tensile Properties

Improvements in Young's modulus were achieved in the short-fibre and particle-reinforced alloys. Data in Tables 2 and 3 illustrate an increase of \approx 30% in both composite types with values in the range 90 - 95 GPa. The SiC particle reinforcement appears to be more efficient in raising modulus, e.g. 10% by volume addition approaches the increase given by 20% of Al₂O₃ short fibres.

Table 2 Tensile properties of silicon carbide particle-reinforced alloys

Alloy Type and Reinforcement	Heat-treated Condition	Young's Modulus GPa	0.2% Proof Stress MPa	Tensile Strength MPa	Elongation %
2014	T6	73.8	437	489	7.4
2014 + SiC	T8	93.8	484	521	6.9
6061	T6	69.0	240	264	12.3
6061 + SiC	T8	91.9	321	343	3.8

Both types of reinforcement increase the 0.2% proof stress and tensile strength of each alloy; see Tables 2 and 3. The amount of the increase does vary with the type of matrix alloy. Addition of SiC particles to the higher strength 2014 alloy promotes the lowest increase, i.e. 47 MPa in proof stress and 32 MPa in tensile strength. The

Table 3 Tensile properties of ϵ -alumina short-fibre reinforced alloys

Alloy Type and Reinforcement	Heat-Treated Condition	Young's Modulus GPa	0.2% Proof Stress MPa	Tensile Strength MPa	Elongation %
Al-3.5%Cu	T6	70.6	174	261	14.0
Al-3.5%Cu - Al ₂ O ₃ Sample (1)	T6	90.3	235	353	2.2
Al-3.5%Cu - Al ₂ O ₃ Sample (2)	T6	94.4	242	394	3.2

largest increase in proof stress is in the particle-reinforced 6061 alloy with an increment of 81 MPa, whilst the largest change (133 MPa) in tensile strength is given by samples of the Al_2O_3 -reinforced Al-3.5%Cu alloys taken from the stronger of the two squeeze castings. Although the same alloy melt was used for both castings, and preforms were made to similar specifications, variations in modulus and, more particularly, in tensile strength (41 MPa) were noted.

The addition of 10% SiC particles to 2014 alloy did promote a small increase in % elongation to failure, i.e. in an alloy which showed the smallest strength increase. Elongation of the 6061 alloy is reduced significantly by the same level of reinforcement, i.e. from 12.3% to 3.8%. A slightly greater reduction in ductility was noted with the introduction of 20% Al_2O_3 fibres into the Al-3.5%Cu alloy.

2. Fatigue Behaviour

Tests on 20% Al_2O_3 short-fibre reinforced Al-3.5%Cu alloy in the T6 condition under zero-tension conditions show improvement over the unreinforced alloy when they are plotted in the form of S - N plots; see Fig. 1.

Fig. 1 S - N plots for Al-3.5%Cu alloy (T6 condition) with and without S- Al_2O_3 fibres. Samples from a stronger (S) and weaker (W) casting were used.

Samples taken from the higher tensile strength casting give the high stress data at short and long lives. Under low-stress high-cycle conditions, the unreinforced alloy and the lower strength reinforced casting give a similar fatigue strength, i.e. 185 MPa at 10^6 cycles; this rises to 205 MPa with the stronger casting. These represent 68%, 52%, and 52% of the UTS values of matrix, weaker and stronger composite respectively. Under high stress conditions, e.g. at 2×10^4 cycles, the fatigue strength of both composites were 25 - 40 MPa above those of the unreinforced alloy.

The unreinforced high strength 2014 alloy in the T6 condition shows superior fatigue properties to the 6061 alloy in a similar condition; see Fig. 2. At 10^6 cycles the fatigue strength of 2014 alloy was 210 MPa, and that of 6061 was 50 MPa below at 160 MPa. Introducing 10% SiC particles into the 2014 alloy and giving a T8 treatment produce an increase in fatigue strength under high-stress low-cycle and low-stress high-cycle conditions. The fatigue strength of the reinforced alloy at 10^6 cycles was 220 MPa; this represented 42% of the composite tensile strength. Reinforcing the 6061

alloy in the T8 condition with 10% SiC promoted an increase in fatigue strength at 2×10^4 cycles, 60 MPa over the unreinforced T6 alloy, whilst at 10^6 cycles there is a closer approach of the composite value to that of the unreinforced alloy. The composite fatigue strength at 10^6 cycles was 180 MPa, which is 52% of its tensile strength. It was noticed that there is a significant degree of scatter in the fatigue plots for both particle-reinforced alloys.

Fig. 2 S - N plots for 2014 and 6061 alloy (T6 and T8 conditions) with and without α -SiC particles.

3. Initiation and Growth of Fatigue Cracks

From the polished surfaces of the four-point bend samples of the $8\text{-Al}_2\text{O}_3$ -reinforced alloy, replicas were taken at a regular number of cycle intervals. At a stress amplitude ($\Delta\sigma$) of 215 MPa, cracks were found to initiate after 10^3 cycles. This took place at a number of sites over the surface. Fig. 3 (a) - (c) demonstrates how a crack has initiated at the sharp corner of a ceramic particle (piece of "shot") $\approx 20 - 25 \mu\text{m}$ in size. After 5×10^3 cycles, the crack has grown $\approx 7 \mu\text{m}$ from the corner into the matrix. By 2×10^4 cycles, the original crack has increased in length to $\approx 30 \mu\text{m}$, whilst a second crack had initiated and run along the particle-matrix interface and entered the matrix and grown in the opposite direction to the initial crack to a length of $55 \mu\text{m}$. Doubling the number of cycles to 4×10^6 increased the crack lengths to $40 \mu\text{m}$ and $70 \mu\text{m}$ respectively. These measurements of crack length have been taken perpendicular to loading direction, and they take no account of the deviatory crack growth pattern. The deviatory growth arises from the interaction of the crack with the reinforcing fibres in its path. Often the interaction takes place at the fibre ends. This can lead to the situation in Fig. 3c, where the crack has bifurcated by means of a crack being deflected at one end of the fibre and another crack initiating at the other. Fig. 3 (d) shows another crack which has initiated at a fibre end and has also followed a tortuous path of propagation.

4. Fractography

The fracture surfaces of the $8\text{-Al}_2\text{O}_3$ -reinforced alloy produced in a tensile test specimen showed evidence of fibre pull-out and ductile matrix failure. Fig. 4 (a) - (c) shows various parts of a fracture surface produced after 5×10^5 stress cycles at $\Delta\sigma = 210$ MPa. Initiation of the fatigue crack has taken place at the edge of the sample (see Fig. 4 (a)). In this region, the matrix is flat and then becomes rougher as the crack propagates further into the section (see Fig. 4 (b)). Observation made

Fig. 3 Replicated fatigue crack growth produced on the surface of a sample of δ - Al_2O_3 -reinforced alloy after (a) 0 cycles, (b) 5×10^3 cycles, (c) 2×10^4 cycles and (d) a second crack after 2×10^4 cycles. ($\Delta\sigma = 215$ MPa)

on fatigue samples produced on samples from the two squeeze castings revealed that there was less evidence of fibre pull-out in the higher strength composite. An examination was also made of fracture surfaces of samples which failed at lower stresses, i.e. $\sigma_{\text{max}} = 165$ MPa at 10^6 cycles. Crack initiation again took place at the edge of the sample but in a fibre-free region (see Fig. 4 (d)).

The fracture surfaces of tensile samples of the 2014 and 6061 alloys, unreinforced and reinforced with α -SiC particles, show similar characteristics. These surfaces have a number of flat matrix regions ($\approx 15 \mu\text{m}$ in size) interspersed with regions showing ductile failure. SiC particles were present in the surface, but there was little evidence of particle fracture. In the fatigue samples, the surfaces were again flat, and there was little difference between samples with and without reinforcement (see Fig. 5 (a) and (b)). Sections taken perpendicular to the fracture face were ground and polished and examined in the optical microscope. This confirmed that the crack path passed mainly through the matrix material and only on a few occasions (see Fig. 6 (a) and (b)) did it coincide with SiC particles. There was little evidence of SiC particle fractures in the fatigue regions of failure.

Fig. 4 Fracture surfaces produced during zero-tension fatigue tests on δ - Al_2O_3 -reinforced alloy: (a) general view of fracture surface, (b) initiation region, (c) intermediate region with $\Delta\sigma = 210$ MPa and $N_f = 5 \times 10^5$ cycles; (d) initiation region in fibre-free zone in sample subjected to $\Delta\sigma = 165$ MPa and $N_f = 10^6$ cycles.

Fig. 5 Fatigue fracture surfaces produced on (a) unreinforced 2014 alloy and (b) α -SiC reinforced 2014 alloy.

Fig. 6 Polished sections taken adjacent to fracture in a fatigue specimen of α -SiC-reinforced composite showing (a) fatigue and tension regions and (b) the fatigue region at higher magnification.

DISCUSSION

The results described in this paper demonstrate that either short fibres or particles can be introduced into intermediate strength aluminium alloys to promote increases in proof stress, tensile strength and fatigue life. These findings are in accord with previous findings^{5,6} that fatigue performance of a given alloy is enhanced by the introduction of reinforcement, provided that such fibres and particles are capable of providing additional tensile strength. It is also of interest to note that both particles and short fibres, in their respective alloy matrices, are capable of providing a fatigue strength at 10^6 cycles, which is $\approx 50\%$ of the tensile strength. This points towards a similarity of effect which is associated with both forms of reinforcement. Examination of fracture surfaces and the observations on fatigue crack initiation and growth indicate some caution in taking this simplistic view of fatigue in all types of discontinuous MMC's.

1. Fatigue Failure in Short-Fibre Composites

A comparison of the observations made in this paper should be carried out with those reported on the use of δ - Al_2O_3 to reinforce 99.5% aluminium and a higher strength 2618A alloy⁵. Reinforcement of the 99.5% aluminium matrix increased its tensile and fatigue strengths. With 2618A alloy, the tensile strength was not increased by the addition of 20% δ - Al_2O_3 fibre, nor were its fatigue properties. This kind of behaviour was related to fibre-matrix interface conditions which existed in this 2618A alloy. The alloy contained 1.25% magnesium, and observations have clearly shown that presence of magnesium promotes interaction with fibre surfaces which contain silica⁹. A major crack which initiated in a large ceramic particle was able to propagate into and more directly through the matrix and fibres under fatigue conditions. In the Al-3.5%Cu composite tested in this paper and in the 99.5% aluminium matrices, cracks initiated at short-fibre or particle-matrix interfaces. Propagation took place in a deviatoric fashion as the crack ran from fibre to fibre and the fracture surface always involved the fibre-matrix interface. In places, cracks came to a halt at fibre surfaces; cracking nevertheless continued in the vicinity at other interface positions in the same or adjacent fibres.

The fatigue strength of the two castings of the δ - Al_2O_3 -reinforced Al-3.5%Cu alloy show some differences. With the high strength casting, there is less scatter, and a number of specimens run out at maximum stresses in excess of 200 MPa after 6×10^7 cycles. These observations also relate to an increase in tensile strength of 41 MPa between these castings. Examination of matrix microhardness in the T6 condition in both castings gave similar values ($116 \pm 3\text{H}_v$); composite densities were virtually the same. This would appear to demonstrate similarities in matrix properties and fibre contents. Other reasons, such as fibre distribution and aspect ratio, may begin to influence the situation. Observations on sections did not reveal significant differences in fibre lengths, but some variations in the frequency of finding

fibre-free zones was noted. This observation also relates to the fractographic work on a shorter life failure in a sample taken from the weaker casting. Fig. 5 (d) demonstrates that the crack has initiated in a fibre-free zone. Other parts of the fracture surfaces also show some differences, with samples from the higher strength casting having less fibre pull-out. This would suggest the fibre-matrix bond strength had been increased in the processing operation. This might be influenced by minor changes in processing conditions, such as melt temperature and cooling rate. During the cool, the matrix, because of its higher expansion coefficient, will contract on to the fibres. If the above conditions changed, the compressive stresses acting on the fibre-matrix interface may be enhanced, thus promoting a more effective fibre-matrix bond.

2. Fatigue Failure in Particulate Composites

The introduction of SiC particles at the 10% level has brought improvements in the fatigue behaviour of 2014 and 6061 alloys in the T6 condition. In the case of the 6061, the improvement takes place particularly under high-stress low-cycle conditions of testing. Examination of the fracture surface shows a much flatter fracture than was the case with the δ -Al₂O₃ short-fibre composites. Metallographic sections taken adjacent to the fracture face also reveal only few particles being directly involved in the failure process and little evidence of particle failure. These observations are not in accord with those of Shang and Ritchie⁹, who have demonstrated with an Al-Zn-Mg-Cu alloy containing 15 - 20% SiC particles, that the particles crack ahead of the main fatigue crack, and this promotes crack deviation and bridging. It is possible that three factors may influence these observations:

- A. The nature of the particle-matrix bond in a system produced by powder metallurgy (Al-Zn-Mg-Cu matrix) and the one reported here, which was produced by spray forming may be different;
- B. different forms of silicon carbide particles;
- C. the volume fraction of particles present.

If particles or particle-matrix interfaces do not crack, then crack initiation ahead of the main crack will not take place, at least not for these reasons. But if only very limited numbers of particles or interfaces crack, then the volume fraction of particles may begin to influence the situation. At lower volume fractions, as with the current work, the incidence of such cracking is small; the main crack does not deviate significantly, nor is there evidence of much crack branching.

If the presence of the particles does not cause effective crack stopping or deviation, then the main reason for improvements in fatigue performance of the composite will arise because of the improvements in the elastic modulus and the high rate of work hardening in the plastic zone at the crack tip. Both of these factors will reduce effective crack opening displacement. These factors may be more influential under high-stress low-cycle conditions of test.

CONCLUSIONS

(i) The results obtained on both particulate and short-fibre materials demonstrate that if the reinforcement increases the tensile strength of the matrix, then fatigue performance will also show improvement.

(ii) Although both particulate and short-fibre reinforcements gave fatigue failure stresses (at 10⁶ cycles) which are \approx 50% of tensile strength, it has been shown that different crack initiation and growth mechanisms are taking place.

(iii) In the δ -Al₂O₃-reinforced Al-3.5%Cu alloy, the crack initiation takes place at fibre ends or at the corners of pieces of "shot". Cracks, as they propagate, are deflected by fibres and follow fibre-matrix interfaces. This leads to a fracture face which has irregular topography.

(iv) The variation in tensile strength and fatigue performance which has been noted from casting to casting in the δ -alumina short-fibre composites may be explained by the positive effects of compressive stresses acting on the fibre-matrix interfaces and the negative aspects of fibre-free zones.

(v) SiC-particulate reinforcement does not appear to influence crack initiation and growth significantly. Low volume fraction of reinforcement (10%), good particle-matrix bonding and particle strength may be the major factors influencing these observations.

(vi) Increases in elastic modulus and work-hardening rate by the presence of particles and short fibres can improve fatigue performance.

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